

A molecular dynamics simulation of methane adsorption in Single Walled Carbon Nanotube Bundles.

Sergi Vela, Fermín Huarte-Larrañaga*

*Department of Physical Chemistry and Institut de Química Teòrica i Computacional
(IQTUCUB)
Universitat de Barcelona
Barcelona, Spain*

Abstract

The physisorption of methane in idealized bundles of single walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) is investigated in detail in this work employing computational . Several aspects related to the possible application of nanotubes as fuel gas containers are analyzed employing molecular dynamics simulations. The influence of the nanotube diameter on the adsorption capacity of the material and the distribution of the adsorbate are examined by considering bundles of carbon nanotubes with different morphologies. An increase of the load capacity with the nanotube diameter is observed, together with a qualitative change in the distribution of the adsorbed molecules. The effect of porosity is also studied from the point of view of the nanotube separation, finding that this leads to a significant increase in storage capacity in the case of bundles made of small diameter nanotubes. The role of temperature as a possible uptake/release triggering variable is also examined.

*Corresponding author

Email address: `fermin.huarte@ub.edu` (Fermín Huarte-Larrañaga)

1. Introduction

Natural gas presents some relevant advantages with respect to other conventional fuels, being naturally abundant and their combustion less aggressive with the environment. On the other hand, it has a low heat of combustion per unit volume and it usually needs to be compressed (up to 25MPa) to be used in gas-fueled vehicles [1], implying a larger economical cost in the design and manufacture of fuel containers. Alternatively, the physisorption of natural gas in highly porous nanostructured materials offers a very high potential for mobility purposes and large-scale applications[2, 3]. The heat of adsorption for the physisorption of methane on different substrates generally lies in the 10-20 kJ mol⁻¹ energy range and there is a remarkable direct correlation of surface area with adsorption capacity irrespective of the chemistry of the adsorbent material[4]. However, such gas containers are not available and development in the design of adsorbent materials is still necessary to achieve the desired goal. This area of research has experienced an increasing activity in the last decade where the combination of experimental and theoretical work has yielded first promising results, such as the use of open metal-organic frameworks [5–9], coordination polymers [10], or highly packed organic calixarene crystals [11, 12].

Among the different types of nanostructures made of organic or inorganic materials, carbon nanotubes are regarded as extremely promising candidates for their application in material science [13]. The intrinsic high porosity of a lightweight network of single-wall graphitic channels has led to the investigation of their possible nanotechnological applications, such as fillers in polymer matrices, molecular tanks, biosensors, and many others. Among these, the

adsorption of gases in carbon based materials has been intensively studied both experimentally and theoretically, focusing on the optimization of the nanopore structure as a gas-storage media [14–18]. SWCNT bundles seem therefore to offer a particularly suitable solution for on-board fuel storage but a fully detailed understanding of the adsorption process is of great value for future practical applications.

The properties of the molecules confined in nanostructures are different from those of the bulk gaseous or condensed phases. Investigating the molecular behavior inside a nanotube is experimentally difficult, given the very small scale of the system. Molecular simulation techniques have appeared as valuable tools to obtain insight into the properties of fluids confined in micropores [19]. To cite a few recent examples, the behavior of water inside Au nanotubes [20] or the quantum sieving of isotopes [21] have been simulated.

In the present work we investigate some basic aspects of the uptake of natural gas by carbon nanotube-based materials. In particular, we have studied theoretically the physisorption of methane molecules in SWCNT bundles, employing molecular dynamics (MD) simulations and atom-atom pair potentials to generate the force fields. The first theoretical studies on the physisorption of methane in carbon-based porous materials go back to the early 90s [22–24]. Methane storage in nanotubes has been afterwards tackled from a theoretical perspective by Cao [25], who applied Grand Canonical Monte Carlo Simulations to optimize the adsorption capacity of triangular SWCNT arrays, and by Kowalczyk [26] who considered structureless nanotubes and pseudospherical methane molecules. Further computational works have followed, investigating the effect of doping the nanostructure with nitrogen [27]

or focusing on the separation of hydrogen (H_2 and CH_4) mixtures [28, 29]. Here, the physisorption of pure methane in bundles of single wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) is investigated by analyzing the influence of the material porosity on the storage capacity and the adsorbate distribution. The porosity of the material is varied in two ways, considering nanotubes of different diameter and increasing the intertube separation in the bundles. In spite of its importance, other parameters rather than only the total load capacity of the adsorbent material need to be considered, such as the reactivity of the contained walls, mechanical resistance, or even the thermodynamical variables that can control the uptake/delivery process. The possible role of the temperature acting as an agent triggering the uptake or release of the fuel gas is also analyzed in our work.

The manuscript is accordingly organized as follows: firstly, a general description of the simulation procedure is given in Section 2. Relevant details about the *construction* of the SWCNT bundles, the molecular dynamics simulations as well as the interaction potentials employed are described in this section. In Section 3, the results of the different simulations analyzing how the load capacity of the material and the adsorbate distribution are affected by the porosity of the bundles. To conclude the section, the results of macro-canonical simulations are employed to investigate the possible role of temperature as a variable to control the release process. Our conclusions are summarized in Section 4.

2. Method

Methane physisorption has been studied on three types of carbon nanotube aggregates. The carbon nanotubes have not been considered isolated *as grown* carbon nanotubes but rather forming *idealized* bundles of open-ended nanotubes. This kind of nanotubes are obtained experimentally after heat treatment in the presence of O₂ and CO₂ [30, 31]. Our SWCNTs are grouped in bundles with hexagonal slab geometry and a nanotube separation of 3Å. These bundles are assumed to be *pure*, *i.e.* made of SWCNT of the same chirality and length (32.71 Å), and unaffected by adsorption of the gas. The geometry of the nanotube bundles is sketched in Figure 1 from a zenithal point of view, identifying the nanotubes as circles. The dashed line polygon indicates the simulation cell (*z* coordinate is mapped out) in which the MD simulations are performed employing periodic boundary conditions. We have studied bundles made of *zig-zag* nanotubes with increasing diameter, namely (10,0), (15,0), and (20,0). The geometrical parameters corresponding to the simulation cell for each SWCNT bundle are listed in Table 1. It should be however emphasized that the bundles in our simulations are idealized and therefore not completely realistic, *i.e.* no Hydrogen atoms nor functional groups are considered at the open caps of the nanotubes. This would actually imply, in a real situation, having radicals and a much different reactivity. Similarly to previous works [32], this issue is neglected in our simulation, given our interest in exclusively physisorption effects.

The DLPOLY [33] molecular dynamics computational code has been used for the dynamics simulations. At each step of the trajectory, the intramolecular forces in methane have been calculated employing a harmonic potential

chirality	ϕ (Å)	X (Å)	Y (Å)	nc
(10,0)	7.84	21.68	18.77	1280
(15,0)	11.76	29.52	25.56	1920
(20,0)	15.68	37.36	32.35	2560

Table 1: (m,n) Single-walled Carbon nanotube bundles studied: ϕ is the nanotube diameter, X,Y represent the (x,y)-lattice vectors of the periodic slab, and nc labels the number of C atoms embedded in the simulation cell.

Figure 1: Sketch of the nanotube bundles with (x,y) hexagonal slab symmetry, dashed polygon indicates the boundary of the periodic simulation slab.

pair	ϵ (Kcal/mol)	σ (Å)
C-C	0.05565	3.400
C-H	0.06069	3.184
H-H	0.06618	2.963

Table 2: Lennard Jones parameters for the different intermolecular pair interactions.

for both the C-H bond length ($k=340$ kcal mol⁻¹ Å⁻², $r_0=1.09$ Å) and H-C-H bond angle ($k=35$ kcal mol⁻¹, $\theta_0=109.5^\circ$). The intermolecular forces are obtained using atom-atom pair potentials, namely a Lennard-Jones (LJ) potential is employed:

$$U(r_{ij}) = 4\epsilon \left[\left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right]. \quad (1)$$

The parameters employed are listed in Table 2. In spite of the well-known limitations of this kind of description, the isotropic LJ potential has already been used in previously published simulations and it is acknowledged to be representative of the interactions present in the SWCNT-methane system [22–25, 29, 34]. An alternative for future developments could be to use more sophisticated models than the atom-atom pair potential, such as the recently developed atom-bond potentials [35] and derive the interaction energy parameters from high level *ab initio* calculations [36]. Nevertheless, the features described in this paper and the conclusions which are drawn are not essentially affected by a more involved force field. Finally, it should be noted that no force field parameters are used for the C(SWCNT)-C(SWCNT) interaction and therefore internal motion of the nanotubes is not included in our simulations.

Two strategies have been followed in order to simulate gas adsorption in the nanotubes. First, a procedure has been used, in which the nanostructure is progressively loaded with methane by carrying out consecutive molecular dynamics simulations. This procedure can be intuitively seen as a *progressive stationary state gas loading* of the nanostructure. The scheme employed has been the following: in an initial run a total of 30 methane molecules (60 in the case of the (20,0) SWCNT) are placed on the upper side of the SWCNT bundle, at a distance between 3.0 Å and 10.0 Å (along the z -axis). This distance range was chosen in order to start the dynamics in a situation where the gas molecules were neither sitting right on the Lennard-Jones minimum nor beyond its attractive range. The CH₄ molecules are distributed randomly within the two distances and inside the x,y hexagonal unit cell. A snapshot of a possible initial configuration is shown in Figure 2.

Starting from this initial configuration, a molecular dynamics trajectory is carried out within the microcanonical NVE ensemble, imposing periodic boundary conditions only on the x,y directions and leaving z unbound (i.e. methane molecules are free to diffuse away from the nanotubes). Each MD trajectory is first equilibrated during 0.4 ns at a temperature around 273K (velocity scaling every 100 steps) and then propagated for another 1.6 ns, with a time step of 2 fs, using the Verlet algorithm[37]. A cutoff radius of 9 Å is applied to the non-bonding interactions in order to speed up the computation of the forces.

After 2 ns of simulation the trajectory is stopped and adsorption of the methane molecules in the SWCNT bundles is analyzed. The fraction of trapped (physisorbed) molecules is compared to the fraction which has dif-

Figure 2: Snapshot (side view) of a possible initial configuration of the MD simulation.

fused away from the carbon surface. If the SWCNT bundle is not saturated, the adsorbed methane molecules are conserved in the calculation and a new group of molecules is placed within the same z -range as the previous one (again, random initial conditions). Next, a MD simulation is performed under the same conditions described previously. The procedure is repeated until there is no net adsorption, i.e. the nanotube bundle is saturated. This procedure of consecutive MD simulations can thus be seen as a stationary flux of gas flowing over a surface made of uniform open-ended $(n,0)$ SWCNT. A similar procedure to the present one has been employed in previous works [38, 39].

The second strategy consisted in performing MD simulations employing the macrocanonical NVT ensemble and periodic boundary conditions in all three directions of space. The z lattice vector has been chosen of length 73 Å allowing for a $L/2$ Å gap (where L is the length of the nanotube) above and below the nanotube bundle. The storage capacity of the material has been analyzed for different gas pressures and temperatures in order to find out whether Temperature is a valid variable to control the performance of a gas container.

3. Results and Discussion

The gas loading procedure described above has been applied to bundles of SWCNT with chirality (10,0), (15,0), and (20,0). The gravimetric density of adsorbed CH₄ % wt, calculated as $m_{ads}/m_{total} \times 100$ is plotted in Figure 3 as a function of the simulation time. The bottom leftmost panel contains the load curve of the initial run where the SWCNT-bundle is clean from any adsorbate. The following panels (from left to right, and upwards) represent

Figure 3: Methane-load (% wt) as function of time for the three different SWCNT-bundles studied.

the consecutive simulations of the progressive loading procedure. A methane molecule is considered to be physisorbed if the center of mass is less than 3\AA away from the bundle upper/lower end. The amount of gas adsorbed in the SWCNT bundle rises steeply in the first simulations. As the nanotubes are progressively filled, the load curves do not rise so sharply anymore due to the repulsion between the physisorbed molecules and the incoming ones.

Equilibrium is rapidly achieved for the (10,0) SWCNT (black line in Fig. 3) and a constant methane load of approximately 4% wt is conserved after a few nanoseconds and the following runs. Instead, for the larger (15,0) diameter nanotubes (red line) the progressive loading needed to be repeated up to five times until the nanotube is saturated. The result of the simulation is shown as a red line in Figure 3, reaching an equilibrium load of approx-

imately 6.0 % wt. The third type of SWCNT for which physisorption has been investigated are those with (20,0) chirality. The diameter of the tube is doubled with respect to the (10,0) and consequently a bigger proportion of CH₄ molecules is adsorbed inside the tubes. The same procedure as in the previous cases has been followed, repeating the gas loading procedure until there is no net adsorption. The nanotube bundle is saturated after 7 consecutive MD runs, achieving a gravimetric density value of 6.6% wt, corresponding to 136 molecules of methane. The reported final gas storage capacities of the three nanostructures are listed in Table 3 both in terms of gravimetric and volumetric densities. As expected, the maximum load of methane is achieved in the nanostructure composed of nanotubes with the largest diameter. This is in agreement with previous experimental and theoretical observations. However, this dependence of the load capacity on the nanotube diameter is not linear and the increase in (15,0) with respect to the (10,0) bundle is larger than in the (20,0) case, in relative terms. Another interesting observation can be made by comparing the values reported in Table 3 and the time evolution of the corresponding curves in Fig. 3. Although the final storage capacity increases with the diameter of the nanotube the trend is precisely the opposite in the initial stages of the loading procedure (first three panels). In spite of the greater adsorption capacity of the larger diameter nanotubes, the smaller diameter ones are more effective in trapping the gas molecules under low coverage conditions.

As it has been discussed in the Introduction section, performing molecular simulation of fluids in micropores provides the opportunity of obtaining interesting information at a microscopic level. The van der Waals (intermolecular)

and internal energies averaged over the adsorbed methane molecules are given in Table 3 for all three nanotube bundles studied. In order to obtain these values, a final simulation has been run starting from the saturated nanostructure with no gas molecules outside the nanotube bundle. An additional periodic boundary condition has been added in the simulation cell in this final calculation in order to have a fixed volume and compute estimates of the methane pressure, also listed in Table 3. **Positive and negative values of the pressure can be identified in the table, depending on the nanotube diameter.** This issue will be discussed later in the paper. The values of E_{vdw} and E_{int} , statistically averaged throughout the MD trajectory, are divided by the number of adsorbate molecules. The adsorption and internal energies can be compared between the three nanobundles given that the temperature value at the end of all three simulations is nearly the same: 263.3 ± 3.1 K ((10,0)), 264.2 ± 4.3 K ((15,0)), and 267.5 ± 2.5 K ((29,0)). The calculated average intermolecular energies (E_{vdw}) evidence that, in spite of the smaller load capacity, the smaller diameter nanopores provide a higher stabilization effect. This energy difference might well be the cause of the higher effectiveness of small radius SWCNT in trapping CH_4 at low coverage described in the previous paragraph. It must be however noted that this interaction energy contains as well the methane – methane interaction. As it will be discussed in the last section, the fact that methane molecules are strongly physisorbed to the nanostructure is not necessarily convenient in the case of a fuel container where the release process is equally important to the uptake one. The average internal energy of the adsorbed molecules is shown in the same table (fifth column), with values comparable to those ob-

SWCNT	% wt	D (kg/m ³)	P (atm)	E_{vdw} (kcal/mol)	E_{int} (kcal/mol)
(10,0)	3.90 ± 0.10	61.9	351.5	-11.510 ± 0.079	1.720 ± 0.080
(15,0)	5.79 ± 0.05	82.9	-278.7 ± 3.3	-7.566 ± 0.053	1.853 ± 0.063
(20,0)	6.64 ± 0.05	91.4	-674.6	-5.652 ± 0.073	2.084 ± 0.061

Table 3: Methane saturated carbon nanotube bundles. Averaged equilibrium values at approx. 273 K and associated statistical error: adsorption capacity, expressed in gravimetric and volumetric density, methane pressure. Fifth and sixth columns: average internal and intermolecular interaction energies of the adsorbed molecules. Statistical

tained in pure gaseous methane bulk simulations (it should be kept in mind that a harmonic oscillator is used as a force field generator and therefore the equilibrium value is $E_{int}=0$).

The process is highly dynamic and, even when physisorbed in the nanotube, the gas molecules move actively in the bundle. In order to illustrate this, two representative trajectories are plotted in Figure 4 corresponding to molecules physisorbed in the (15,0) SWNT- bundle. The trajectories correspond to the motion of the center of mass (c.o.m.) of the selected molecules mapped on the xy-plane and thus the motion in the z-coordinate cannot be observed. These show how the adsorbed molecules constantly move around the bundle and only in some cases they seem to be somewhat confined. The adsorption equilibrium state is therefore highly dynamic and the physisorbed molecules move constantly, rather than occupy a fixed most stable position. Thus, it must be kept in mind that, although we refer to adsorption sites these are not static fixed geometries with an absolute minimum energy.

Rather than actually reporting quantitative accurate storage capacity values, our work is aimed at the rationalization of the adsorption process. An

Figure 4: Representative trajectories of adsorbed CH_4 molecules in the (15,0) nanotube bundle. Units are Angstrom on both X and Y axes.

important result coming out from our molecular studies, which may be of aid in a rational design of efficient gas containers, is the distribution of the adsorbate. By identifying the relevant (dynamic) physisorption sites, ideas can be developed on how the capacity of the material can be increased. Once the three SWCNT-bundles have been saturated, we have analyzed the distribution of the adsorbed CH_4 molecules inside the nanostructure. First, we have observed that the adsorbate density distribution is nearly uniform along the z direction (along the nanotube axes). This is especially the case of the (15,0) and (20,0) bundles, while the (10,0) distribution shows some minor oscillations. This uniform distribution allows us to eliminate the z coordinate mapping the probability density onto the xy plane, making the analysis much simpler. Figure 5 shows the distribution of methane molecules adsorbed inside the nanotube bundles, projected on the xy -plane for the three SWCNT-bundles under study. In order to observe the differences, one must

first notice the different xy scale of the plots, where the leftmost panel ((10,0) bundle) covers one fourth of the region covered by the rightmost (20,0) one. Given that the values of the density distribution vary very promptly, no scale or color code is given for the intensities in the plot, which is only meant for interpretative purposes. In the case of the smallest diameter nanotubes (left hand panel, Fig. 5), the xy density map shows sharp maxima coinciding with the x,y coordinates of the nanotube axes. This means that the adsorbed gas molecules are tightly confined forming chains along the nanotube axes. The centers of mass of the adsorbed methane molecules are at an average distance of approximately 3.9\AA of the nanotube walls, very close to the σ_{CC} Lennard-Jones parameter. If a molecule comes closer to the nanotube wall, it rapidly feels the interatomic repulsive wall. Thus, although the energetic stabilization is large in the case of the narrow nanotubes (see Table 3), the restrictions on the center of mass motion of the adsorbed molecules might cause a larger contribution in the opposite direction and explain the high affinity but low capacity of the (10,0) bundle. Considering next the (15,0) nanotube bundle (middle panel), we see that as the nanotube diameter increases (and also the material porosity), the distribution of the adsorbed methane changes significantly, forming now a cylinder or a "crown" (see middle panel in Fig. 5) coaxial to the nanotube walls. Thus, although in the (15,0) SWCNT-bundle the stabilization energy is decreased by a 33% with respect to the (10,0) structure, the adsorbate molecules are less constrained. This would explain the higher maximum load observed. In the case of the nanotubes with the largest nanotube cavity, the (20,0) bundle, the situation is qualitatively similar to the previous one, a cylindrical shell of adsorbed methane molecules

Figure 5: Adsorbed methane probability distribution in the (10,0) (left hand panel), (15,0) (middle panel), and (20,0) (right hand panel) nanotube bundles: Mapping on the xy -plane.

is formed inside the nanotube cavities. However, a new adsorption site can also be observed with respect to the (15,0) case, methane chains form along the axis of the adsorbed methane shell (much lower intensity in the graph). Nevertheless, this new adsorption site is probably not very meaningful since it is very likely to be caused by $\text{CH}_4 - \text{CH}_4$ interactions.

3.1. Effect of the van der Waals inter-tube separation

Performing MD computer simulation provides the opportunity of testing possible material modifications which may not be easy to obtain experimentally, but yet provide hints about an efficient material design. Following previous studies by Guay for H_2 storage in carbon nanotubes [40] and Cao for CH_4 adsorption in triangular arrays of SWCNTs [25], we have analyzed the possible influence of the van der Waals (VdW) separation gap between the nanotubes that form the bundle. The porosity of the nanotube bundles is essentially the result of the nanotube diameters and the size of the interstices between the nanotube walls. Accordingly, we have focused on the

smallest (10,0) and largest (20,0) diameter nanotubes and generated bundles with an increasing nanotube separation, 3.0, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, and 6.0Å, and we have applied the gas loading procedure. The results of our simulations are summarized in Figure 6 where we plot the adsorption capacity (Fig. 6 (a)) and the intermolecular energy (Fig. 6 (b)) as a function of the VdW gap (δ , in Å). Remarkably, results are very different for the two cases studied. The adsorption capacity of the (20,0) remains essentially unaltered as δ is increased, showing irrelevant oscillations around a 7 %wt saturation value. Similarly, the stabilization energy of the adsorbed molecules does not vary significantly. One may thus conclude that increasing the intertube porosity does not affect physisorption in the case of the (20,0) bundle. Instead, in the case of the (10,0) bundle there is a prompt increase in the gravimetric density when going from a 4.5 Å to a 5.0 Å separation, and the adsorption capacity of the nanostructure is doubled to a value of 8%wt. The intermolecular energy increases in this case, probably a consequence of the higher methane density and the consequent repulsive interactions.

According to this data, one may conclude that, while the nanotube diameter must be indeed large enough to accommodate gas molecules inside the hollow cavity, the adsorption capacity of the material could be greatly enhanced (in the case of small diameter, ϕ) by increasing the intertube porosity. This observation is further confirmed by representing the adsorbate xy probability density plot. Figure 7 shows the adsorbate distribution in the (10,0) bundle corresponding to an intertube separation of 4.5Å (left hand side panel) and 5.0Å (rhs panel). Clearly, the larger VdW gap enables the opening of a new adsorption site that leads to the observed increase in the load

Figure 6: Effect of the van der Waals intertube gap on the storage capacity of the SWCNT-bundle (a) and the corresponding average intermolecular energy experienced by the adsorbed methane molecules (b).

capacity. These are interstitial channels with three-fold symmetry between the outer walls of three adjacent nanotubes. The same exohedral adsorption sites appear in the (20,0) bundle, at a δ_{vdw} value of 4.0\AA , but in this case the new sites do not represent a significant increase in the capacity with respect to the gas adsorbed inside the tube cavities. It is interesting to note that the δ_{vdw} value at which the interstitial sites appear corresponds to the geometric arrangement in which three identical circles of radius $r + \sigma_{CC} + \delta_{vdw}$ (with r being the radius of the nanotube, σ_{CC} the LJ parameter and δ_{CC} the tube separation) at the vertexes of an equilateral triangle share a single intersection point [41, 42].

The opening of the interstitial sites as the van der Waals gap is increased can be explained employing a potential energy surface (PES) model. We have built a PES function which, using the same pair interactions as the MD simulations, evaluates the methane – SWCNT interaction for a single CH_4 molecule and a clean (10,0) nanotube slab, with the intertube δ_{vdw} gap as a

parameter in the intermolecular potential and the same xy periodic boundary conditions. The resulting PES is a function of the cartesian coordinates of the CH₄ center of mass, where (x,y) correspond exactly to the same coordinates as in the MD simulation while the origin of the z coordinates has been reset to the nanotube bundle upper end. Thus, negative values of z correspond to a physisorbed methane molecule. Figure 8 shows a two-dimensional contour plot for $\delta_{vdw}=4 \text{ \AA}$ (lhs) and $\delta_{vdw}=5 \text{ \AA}$ (rhs), considering a Z value of -3 \AA (the adsorbed molecule is 3 \AA inside the bundle). The opening of exohedral sites with sizes comparable to the endohedral ones is clearly predicted by the model potential.

It is therefore reasonable to predict that the efficiency of carbon nanotube based gas storage devices could be significantly improved by using nanotubes of medium diameter and large intertube porosity. This result is in agreement with previous results by Kowalczyk [26] and in the line of the experimental observations reported by Yang [43] and Bekyarova [44], as both authors highlight the importance of adsorption in interstitial channels for the total adsorption capacity of Single Wall Carbon NanoHorns. The technological challenge remains however on the synthesis of nanotube bundles with such morphology.

3.2. Role of temperature as a uptake/release triggering variable

The maximum load capacity presented by a given storage material is certainly an important parameter to be considered when designing gas containers. However, one must also pay attention to other characteristics of the material such as its chemical reactivity, the reversibility of the uptake and release processes, and the different thermodynamical variables that can

Figure 7: Effect of the van der Waals gap: Spatial density distribution of the adsorbed CH_4 molecules in the (10,0) nanotube bundle for two intertube separations, 4.5\AA (left) and 5.0\AA (right), mapped on the xy -plane.

Figure 8: Effect of the van der Waals gap: Contour plot ($Z=-3\text{\AA}$) of a model Potential Energy Surface (kcal/mol) of the CH_4 - SWCNT interaction in a (10,0) nanotube slab. Two intertube separations are considered, 4\AA (left) and 5\AA (right).

trigger this release process [4]. The last part of the present work has focused on investigating the role of temperature as a possible uptake/release triggering variable in methane storage processes. In order to do this, we have run several MD simulations within the macrocanonical NVT ensemble on the SWCNT bundles for different temperature values, analyzing the effect on the gas load. The simulation cell employed in this section differs from the previous one; the system is closed by imposing periodic boundary conditions in all three dimensions of space and therefore the total number of gas molecules (N) is conserved. The length of the simulation box along the Z axis has been chosen to be 72\AA (i.e. twice the length of the nanotubes) and the bundle has been situated in the center of the simulation box, leaving a 18\AA gap above and below the nanostructure. The Berendsen thermostat has been used throughout the MD trajectory to maintain a constant T value.

The (10,0) and (20,0) SWCNT-bundles ($\delta_{vdw}=3\text{\AA}$) have been chosen again as representative examples and the simulations have been carried out for a different number of CH_4 molecules present in the simulation cell at temperature values ranging from 273 to 498 K. Let us note that, although the simulation cell is closed, the methane molecules are not forced to be physisorbed inside the bundles since there is a vacuum gap underneath and above the bundle. In order to give a very qualitative idea of the methane pressure in the simulation cell, Table 4 lists the estimated pressure values at room temperature considering the Van der Waals equation of state. Two values of P are given, one considering the total volume available in the simulation cell (a) and a second one considering only the volume outside the nanostructure (b).

(10,0)			(20,0)			(20,0) (contd.)		
N	(a)	(b)	N	(a)	(b)	N	(a)	(b)
45	55.1	87.8	180	71.5	113.3	330	120.2	224.3
65	75.9	120.5	240	91.4	148.3	360	130.1	263.6
85	95.4	156.5	300	110.5	193.7			

Table 4: Methane pressure (atm) according to the Van der Waals equation of state considering the total volume of the simulation cell (a), and excluding the volume occupied by the nanotube bundle (b). T=298 K and N stands for the number of methane molecules. VdW coefficients for methane: $a=2.283$ (atm l² mol⁻¹) and $b=0.04278$ l mol⁻¹[45]

(10,0)		(20,0)	
N	P (atm)	N	P (atm)
45	34.7 ± 2.5	180	31.1 ± 3.0
65	XX ± YY	300	XX ± YY
85	XX ± YY	360	XX ± YY

Table 5: Methane pressure (atm) in a simulation cell where all volume is available to the gas molecules, no nanotube structure is present. T=298 K and N stands for the number of methane molecules. The column title indicates the volume used in the MD calculation.

(10,0)		(20,0)	
N	P (atm)	N	P (atm)
45	334.9 ± 2.6	180	-288.0 ± 1.8
65	306.2 ± 3.0	300	-283.7 ± 2.2
85	270.3 ± 3.4	360	-297.5 ± 2.4

Table 6: Methane pressure (atm) in a simulation cell where all volume is available to the gas molecules, no nanotube structure is present. T=298 K and N stands for the number of methane molecules. The column title indicates the volume used in the MD calculation.

Figure 9 shows the variation of the gas load of the nanostructure with temperature for the (10,0) and (20,0) bundles for different values of N . The first feature to be noticed is that the effect of the temperature is not particularly suitable for its use as a trigger for gas release. In both cases the gravimetric density of adsorbate has a smooth behaviour as the temperature of the system is varied. This is particularly noticeable in the (10,0) bundle where, raising the temperature from 223 K to 498 K, only a 30% of the stored gas is released. In the larger diameter case, the variation of %wt with T is larger (50%), which makes sense given that E_{vdw} is smaller and the physisorbed molecules are less trapped. In our opinion, our observation is in no contradiction with previous works [26, 46], where a dependence of adsorption with T was reported. However, the variation of %wt with temperature is in all cases too smooth to be used as a sudden release-triggering factor.

A second feature can be noticed from the plots concerning the saturation of the SWCNT bundles. The (10,0) bundle, with tubes with a smaller radius, are saturated already at very low methane pressures, especially at low temperatures. This might indicate that although the smallest radius nanopores cannot allocate as many adsorbate molecules as the large radius observation, they are on the other hand more efficient in trapping gas molecules at low pressures, as the results indicated in Figure 3 already indicated.

In order to give an idea of the methane pressure in the simulation cell, we have compared the pressure data from two kind of simulations: one including the nanostructure and one without it, conserving the same volume, temperature and number of molecules. The results coming out from this comparison are interesting. In the case of the (10,0) nanotube bundle (cell volume is

Figure 9: Storage capacity of (10,0) (bottom) and (20,0) (top) SWCNT-bundles calculated by NVT molecular dynamics calculations. Different colors correspond to simulations with a different number of methane molecules present in the simulation cell, N.

29307.1 Å³) and 45 CH₄ molecules ($\rho=40.8$ kg/m³) at 298 K, the pressure in the simulation with no SWCNT is 34.7 ± 2.5 atm and it increases nearly ten fold to a value of 334.9 atm when the bundle with narrow nanotubes is included in the simulation. This increase can be explained in terms of the low load capacity of nanotube bundle and the strong confinement of the adsorbed molecules. These two factors lead to a large fraction of volume cell which is excluded to the gas molecules, in spite of the attractive CH₄-SWCNT interactions, and the consequent increase of the pressure. The calculation with 180 methane molecules in the volume of the (20,0) simulation (87029.7 Å³) presents a density similar to the previous one, $\rho=54.9$ kg/m³. The pressure obtained from a simulation with only methane molecules is 31.1 ± 3.0 atm and, exactly opposite to the (10,0) case, the pressure decreases to large negative values when the simulation is carried out in the presence of the (20,0) bundle, -288.0 ± 1.8 atm. Negative pressure values have also been listed in Table 3. The pressure calculated in a MD simulation has contributions from the virial and the temperature. The temperature always makes a positive contribution to the pressure, but the virial often works to reduce pressure. The negative sign of the calculated pressure is a consequence of the fixed volume in the NVT ensemble and indicates simply the presence of a net cohesive force in the system. The pressure calculated has contributions from the temperature (always positive) and the virial. This second term can work to reduce the volume if the forces in the system are cohesive. Negative pressures in NVT molecular dynamics are the consequence of negative net cohesive forces in system where the density is fixed CITE MOLECULAR SIMULATION. According to this, we interpret that in the (20,0) bundles the

calculated pressure is a net balance between the desorbed methane molecules and the cohesively adsorbed ones. The (20,0) nanotube bundle not only can accommodate a larger load of methane but the larger nanotube diameter and interstices facilitate the cohesion of the adsorbed gas.

4. Conclusions

The physisorption of methane on single walled carbon nanotubes has been studied from a computational perspective, running molecular dynamics simulations of system formed by a gaseous bulk of methane and bundles of $(n, 0)$ SWCNTs, arranged in hexagonal symmetry. Overall, our results confirm previous observations of an enhancement of the adsorption capacity given by the porosity of the material. We have studied the effect of porosity of the nanotubular material in two ways, varying the diameter of the nanotube inner cavity and the volume of the interstitial channels. We have observed that the smaller diameter nanotubes are efficient in trapping methane molecules and present a larger van der Waals stabilization energy. On the other hand, the adsorbate molecules are much more constrained and the total storage capacity is significantly smaller. However, the maximum load capacity of these materials may be significantly increased if one were to control the separation gap between the tubes in the nanostructures. We have given evidence that this gives rise to interstitial adsorption sites which double the capacity in the case of (10,0) SWCNT-bundles. By performing NVT simulations we have shown that although the adsorption capacity of the material depends with temperature, this might not be a valid parameter to control the (rapid) switching from an uptake to a release process. Single walled carbon nan-

otubes continue to provide us with hints of their applicability as adsorbents for gas storage or gas filtering. However, many important issues remain still open. Future work should be addressed towards the improvement of the force field, consider the nanotube curvature [15, 47], or the internal dynamics of the nanotubes.

Acknowledgements

Prof. Bill Smith from the Daresbury Laboratory (UK) is thanked for helpful discussions in the final form of the manuscript. The authors acknowledge financial support from the Spanish MEC (Project CTQ2009-12215/BQU), and Generalitat de Catalunya (2009SGR17). Also thanks are due to the Centre de Supercomputació de Catalunya CESCA for the allocated super-computing time.

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